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Research Article

**Microwave assisted synthesis and antimicrobial
screening of novel 9-(N-phenyl) - 4, 5-(2'', ''')-
methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-
diamine derivatives using bis-heterocyclic chalcones**

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ABSTRACT

Amino-pyrimidine derivatives were synthesized by simple and clean single pot method using bis-chalcones of different substituted phenyl glutarimides and guanidine nitrate with neutral alumina irradiated under the microwave supported solvent less condition is demonstrated. All the compounds were screened their antimicrobial activities and showed moderate activities. But certain amino-pyrimidines exhibited synergistic and significant activities against *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* fungal genres.

Keywords: N-Phenyl Glutarimides, Bis-heterocyclic chalcones, Amino-pyrimidines and Antimicrobial activity.

INTRODUCTION

The heterocyclic compounds containing nitrogen groups unusually involved in the past researches of heterocyclic chemistry with the development of synthetic methods. Chalcones and cyclic imides perform a significant starring role in the heterocyclic synthesis containing nitrogen groups. Cyclic imides¹ resembling succinimides^{2, 3}, maleimides⁴, phthalimides⁵ and glutarimide⁶ showed antibacterial⁷ and antifungal shielding activities. The substituted heterocyclic imides were developed from cyclic anhydrides⁸, trifluoroacetylation⁹ and bis-heterocyclic analogs¹⁰ by microwave synthesis. Bis-chalcones are prepared by the condensation¹¹ of the substituted ketones and aldehyde groups¹². They are synthesized by utilizing a number of synthetic routes like solid phase cross-aldol condensation, acid catalyst¹³, coupling reaction¹⁴ and microwave assisted synthesis^{15, 16}.

The amino-pyrimidine derivative has been developed by chalcones intermediates with nitrate, chlorides of guanidine cyclized by ring extension of N-C-N

groups. A variety of novel amino-pyrimidines¹⁷, imidopyrimidines¹⁸, pyrido-pyrimidines¹⁹ and substituted pyrimidines from the chalcone intermediates^{20, 21} shown the significant antibacterial and antifungal activities²². Several amino-pyrimidine derivatives exhibited the significant antimicrobial²³, antioxidant²⁴, anti-inflammatory²⁵, anticancer²⁶, anti-plasmodial²⁷, anti-proliferative leukemia²⁸, anti-hyperlipidemic²⁹, breast carcinoma cells³⁰, analgesic³¹, hypoglycemic activities³², apoptosis inducing activities³³ and non-nucleoside pyrimidine exhibits HIV-1: RT preventive³⁴ activities. The synthesis of pyrimidine and amino-pyrimidine derivatives are prepared by conventional method using Claisen-Schmidt condensation coordinating by chalcones³⁵, cyclization of guanidine hydrochloride³⁶, guanidine³⁷ palladium catalyst³⁸, pyrimidines and fused pyrimidines³⁹, malononitriles⁴⁰, formamides⁴¹, thiosemicarbazide⁴², hydroxylamine⁴³ and guanidine nitrate⁴⁴ by using clean, solvent free microwave synthesis⁴⁵.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Material methods:

Melting points of all the synthesized compounds were inscribed and uncorrected by using open glass capillaries. IR spectra were verified on Shimadzu FTIR-8400S and ATR Brucker alpha FT-IR spectrophotometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded on 500.13 MHz by Brucker spectrophotometer. The completion of reaction was observed by thin layer chromatography practicing done on silica glaze aluminium plates by diethyl ether and ethyl acetate 7:3 proportion ratio. All the compounds **5a-j** was synthesized in the microwave oven in hours from bis-chalcones, guanidine nitrate, neutral alumina.

General procedure for the synthesis of bis-chalcones derived from N-phenyl glutarimides:

The bis-chalcones (**3a-j**) derivatives were synthesized by the mixture of 0.1 mole of N-phenyl glutarimides

(**1a-j**) and 0.2 moles of 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzaldehyde in 2 gm of neutral Al₂O₃ under microwave supported solvent free condition on 640W power for 3-6 min. The developed compounds were recrystallized from ethanol (**Scheme – I**)

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-phenylpiperidine-2,6-dione (3a):

Yellowish White Solid; Molecular Formula: C₂₇H₂₃NO₆; Molecular Weight: 457.47; Yield: 79.91%; Melting Point (°C): 78-80 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 71.06; H, 6.98; N, 3.24; FTIR (KBr): >C=O (2-Peaks): 1595 cm⁻¹ and 1672 cm⁻¹, =C-H: 2968 cm⁻¹, aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1455 cm⁻¹, 1513 cm⁻¹ and 1541 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1157 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3320 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (200.13 MHz, CDCl₃, δ ppm): 6.26-7.40 (m, 8H, Ar-H and =CH), 9.87 (s, 1H, -OH), 3.70 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.46 (s, 2H, -CH₂)

Scheme -I: (3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-N-phenylpiperidine-2,6-dione

Scheme -II: 9-(N-phenyl)-4,5-(2',3'-methoxyphenyl)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (5a-j)

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(4-bromophenyl)piperidine-2,6-dione (3b):

Dark Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: $C_{27}H_{22}BrNO_6$; Molecular Weight: 536.37; Yield: 94.37%; Melting Point ($^{\circ}C$): 94-96 $^{\circ}C$; Elemental Analysis: C, 60.88; H, 4.25; N, 2.75; FTIR (KBr): $>C=O$ (2-Peaks): 1667 cm^{-1} and 1689 cm^{-1} , $=C-H$: 3032 cm^{-1} , aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1462 cm^{-1} , 1514 cm^{-1} and 1590 cm^{-1} , Ar-OCH₃: 1172 cm^{-1} , Ar-OH: 3294 cm^{-1} , Ar-Br: 1072 cm^{-1}

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(4-chlorophenyl)piperidine-2,6-dione (3c):

Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: $C_{27}H_{22}ClNO_6$; Molecular Weight: 491.92; Yield: 82.25%; Melting Point ($^{\circ}C$): 76-78 $^{\circ}C$; Elemental Analysis: C, 66.42; H, 4.68; N, 2.99; FTIR (KBr) (Spectra No.-51): $>C=O$ (2-Peaks): 1667 cm^{-1} and 1742 cm^{-1} , $=C-H$: 3030 cm^{-1} , aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1462 cm^{-1} , 1512 cm^{-1} and 1590 cm^{-1} , Ar-OCH₃: 1170 cm^{-1} , Ar-OH: 3287 cm^{-1} , Ar-Cl: 1026 cm^{-1}

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-p-tolylpiperidine-2,6-dione (3d):

Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: $C_{28}H_{25}NO_6$; Molecular Weight: 471.5; Yield: 83.98%; Melting Point ($^{\circ}C$): 95-97 $^{\circ}C$; Elemental Analysis: C, 71.86; H, 5.73; N, 3.55; FTIR (KBr): $>C=O$ (2-Peaks): 1594 cm^{-1} and 1675 cm^{-1} , $=C-H$: 2946 cm^{-1} , aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1459 cm^{-1} , 1514 cm^{-1} and 1596 cm^{-1} , Ar-OCH₃: 1171 cm^{-1} , Ar-OH: 3280 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (500.13 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 6.97-7.48 (m, 5H, Ar-H and $=CH$), 9.78 (s, 1H, -OH), 3.70 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.71 (s, 2H, -CH₂)

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(4-ethoxyphenyl)piperidine-2,6-dione (3e):

Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: $C_{28}H_{25}NO_7$; Molecular Weight: 487.5; Yield: 69.41%; Melting Point ($^{\circ}C$): 68-70 $^{\circ}C$; Elemental Analysis: C, 69.09; H, 5.72; N, 3.20; FTIR (KBr): $>C=O$ (2-Peaks): 1596 cm^{-1} and 1677 cm^{-1} , $=C-H$: 2971 cm^{-1} , aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1460 cm^{-1} , 1514 cm^{-1} and 1596 cm^{-1} , Ar-OCH₃: 1171 cm^{-1} , Ar-OH: 3466 cm^{-1}

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(4-fluorophenyl)piperidine-2,6-dione (3f):

Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: $C_{27}H_{22}FNO_6$; Molecular Weight: 475.47; Yield: 90.84%; Melting Point ($^{\circ}C$): 85-87 $^{\circ}C$; Elemental Analysis: C, 68.81;

H, 4.93; N, 3.33; FTIR (KBr): $>C=O$ (2-Peaks): 1594 cm^{-1} and 1672 cm^{-1} , $=C-H$: 3089 cm^{-1} , aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1426 cm^{-1} , 1513 cm^{-1} and 1594 cm^{-1} , Ar-OCH₃: 1158 cm^{-1} , Ar-OH: 3316 cm^{-1} , Ar-F: 1126 cm^{-1}

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(4-nitrophenyl)piperidine-2,6-dione (3g):

Pale Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: $C_{27}H_{22}N_2O_8$; Molecular Weight: 502.47; Yield: 78.33%; Melting Point ($^{\circ}C$): 93-95 $^{\circ}C$; Elemental Analysis: C, 64.76; H, 4.65; N, 5.85; FTIR (KBr): $>C=O$ (2-Peaks): 1668 cm^{-1} and 1711 cm^{-1} , $=C-H$: 3078 cm^{-1} , aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1460 cm^{-1} , 1512 cm^{-1} and 1590 cm^{-1} , Ar-OCH₃: 1170 cm^{-1} , Ar-OH: 3269 cm^{-1} , Ar-NO₂: 1512 cm^{-1}

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(naphthalen-1-yl)piperidine-2,6-dione (3h):

Whitish Brown Solid; Molecular Formula: $C_{31}H_{25}NO_6$; Molecular Weight: 507.53; Yield: 91.74%; Melting Point ($^{\circ}C$): 88-90 $^{\circ}C$; Elemental Analysis: C, 73.79; H, 5.02; N, 2.98; FTIR (KBr): $>C=O$ (2-Peaks): 1667 cm^{-1} and 1704 cm^{-1} , $=C-H$: 3078 cm^{-1} , aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1429 cm^{-1} , 1460 cm^{-1} , 1511 cm^{-1} , 1589 cm^{-1} and 1667 cm^{-1} , Ar-OCH₃: 1172 cm^{-1} , Ar-OH: 3178 cm^{-1}

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(3-chloro-4-fluorophenyl)piperidine-2,6-dione (3i):

Dark Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: $C_{27}H_{21}ClFNO_6$; Molecular Weight: 509.91; Yield: 82.23%; Melting Point ($^{\circ}C$): 74-76 $^{\circ}C$; Elemental Analysis: C, 63.91; H, 4.69; N, 2.86; FTIR (KBr): $>C=O$ (2-Peaks): 1595 cm^{-1} and 1674 cm^{-1} , $=C-H$: 3027 cm^{-1} , aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1459 cm^{-1} , 1511 cm^{-1} and 1544 cm^{-1} , Ar-OCH₃: 1172 cm^{-1} , Ar-OH: 3309 cm^{-1} , Ar-F: 1172 cm^{-1} , Ar-Cl: 1056 cm^{-1}

(3Z,5Z)-3,5-bis(4-hydroxy-3-methoxybenzylidene)-1-(2,4,5-trichlorophenyl)piperidine-2,6-dione (3j):

Pinkish White Solid; Molecular Formula: $C_{27}H_{20}Cl_3NO_6$; Molecular Weight: 560.81; Yield: 83.03%; Melting Point ($^{\circ}C$): 103-105 $^{\circ}C$; Elemental Analysis: C, 58.58; H, 3.84; N, 2.87; FTIR (KBr): $>C=O$ (2-Peaks): 1669 cm^{-1} and 1694 cm^{-1} , $=C-H$: 3027 cm^{-1} , aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1459 cm^{-1} , 1512 cm^{-1} and 1580 cm^{-1} , Ar-OCH₃: 1170 cm^{-1} , Ar-OH: 3276 cm^{-1} , Ar-2,4,5Cl: 1078 cm^{-1} ; 1H NMR (500.13 MHz, DMSO- d_6 , δ ppm): 6.96-8.10 (m, 5H, Ar-H

and =CH), 9.77 (s, 1H, -OH), 3.40 (s, 3H, -OCH₃), 2.30 (s, 2H, -CH₂)

General procedure for the synthesis of amino-pyrimidines (5a-j):

Amino-pyrimidine (5a-j) derivatives were synthesized by the mixture of 0.2 moles of previously prepared bis-chalcones (3a-j) and 0.4 moles of guanidine nitrate in 2 gm of neutral Al₂O₃ under microwave supported solvent free condition on 640W power for 4-7 minutes. The synthesized compounds were recovered by ethyl acetate and recrystallized by ethanol (Scheme-II)

9-(1-phenyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6a):

Brownish Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: C₂₉H₂₅N₇O₄; Molecular Weight: 535.55; Yield: 80.45%; Melting Point (°C): 89-91 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 65.19; H, 4.71; N, 18.95; FTIR (KBr): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3303 cm⁻¹ and 3365 cm⁻¹, aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1532 cm⁻¹, 1595 cm⁻¹ and 1665 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1293 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3509 cm⁻¹

9-(4'-bromophenyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6b):

Yellowish Orange Solid; Molecular Formula: C₂₉H₂₄BrN₇O₄; Molecular Weight: 614.45; Yield: 76.54%; Melting Point (°C): 99-101 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 56.89; H, 4.21; N, 16.31; FTIR (KBr): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3417 cm⁻¹ and 3461 cm⁻¹, aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1532 cm⁻¹, 1595 cm⁻¹ and 1665 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1293 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3593 cm⁻¹, Ar-Br: 1024 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 6.96-7.56 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 9.77 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 10.27 (s, 1H, -OH), 3.80 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.41 (s, 2H, CH₂)

9-(4'chlorophenyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6c):

Yellowish Solid; Molecular Formula: C₂₉H₂₄ClN₇O₄; Molecular Weight: 570.00; Yield: 83.03%; Melting Point (°C): 88-90 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 61.38; H, 4.67; N, 17.73; FTIR (KBr): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3300 cm⁻¹ and 3370 cm⁻¹, aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1461 cm⁻¹, 1596 cm⁻¹ and 1623 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1268 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3493 cm⁻¹, Ar-Cl: 1028 cm⁻¹

9-(p-tolyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6d):

Whitish Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: C₃₀H₂₇N₇O₄; Molecular Weight: 549.58; Yield: 79.12%; Melting Point (°C): 108-110 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 65.85; H, 5.15; N, 17.98; FTIR (KBr): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3402 cm⁻¹ and 3456 cm⁻¹, aromatic

ring (3-Peaks): 1459 cm⁻¹, 1515 cm⁻¹ and 1592 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1297 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3600 cm⁻¹

9-(4'-methoxyphenyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6e):

Yellowish Green Muddy Solid; Molecular Formula: C₃₀H₂₇N₇O₅; Molecular Weight: 565.58; Yield: 67.25%; Melting Point (°C): 88-90 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 63.86; H, 4.98; N, 17.75; FTIR (KBr): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3316 cm⁻¹ and 3394 cm⁻¹, aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1513 cm⁻¹, 1594 cm⁻¹ and 1667 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1296 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3600 cm⁻¹

9-(4'-fluorophenyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6f):

Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: C₂₉H₂₄FN₇O₄; Molecular Weight: 553.54; Yield: 80.00%; Melting Point (°C): 91-93 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 63.72; H, 4.49; N, 17.98; FTIR (KBr): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3313 cm⁻¹ and 3392 cm⁻¹, aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1513 cm⁻¹, 1594 cm⁻¹ and 1668 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1296 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3500 cm⁻¹, Ar-F: 1158 cm⁻¹

9-(4'-nitrophenyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6g):

Yellow Solid; Molecular Formula: C₂₉H₂₄N₈O₆; Molecular Weight: 580.55; Yield: 70.68%; Melting Point (°C): 123-125 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 60.28; H, 4.67; N, 19.75; FTIR (ATR): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3254 cm⁻¹ and 3355 cm⁻¹, aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1461 cm⁻¹, 1594 cm⁻¹ and 1672 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1265 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3600 cm⁻¹, Ar-NO₂: 1513 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, CDCl₃, δ ppm): 6.96-8.20 (m, 5H, Ar-H), 9.77 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 10.27 (s, 1H, -OH), 3.80 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.38 (s, 2H, CH₂)

9-(naphth-4-yl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6h):

Greyish Brown Solid; Molecular Formula: C₃₃H₂₇N₇O₄; Molecular Weight: 585.61; Yield: 64.60%; Melting Point (°C): 103-105 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 67.76; H, 4.69; N, 16.99; FTIR (KBr): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3299 cm⁻¹ and 3393 cm⁻¹, aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1459 cm⁻¹, 1513 cm⁻¹, 1535 cm⁻¹, 1594 cm⁻¹ and 1669 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1265 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3600 cm⁻¹

9-(3'-chloro-4'-fluorophenyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6i):

Brownish Solid; Molecular Formula: C₂₉H₂₃ClFN₇O₄; Molecular Weight: 587.99; Yield: 72.60%; Melting Point (°C): 84-86 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 59.38; H, 3.89; N, 16.85; FTIR (KBr): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3254 cm⁻¹ and 3324 cm⁻¹, aromatic

ring (3-Peaks): 1543 cm⁻¹, 1595 cm⁻¹ and 1675 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1293 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3501 cm⁻¹, Ar-F: 1158 cm⁻¹, Ar-Cl: 1028 cm⁻¹

9-(2',4',5'-trichlorophenyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (6j):

Whitish Pink Solid; Molecular Formula: C₂₉H₂₂Cl₃N₇O₄; Molecular Weight: 638.89; Yield: 72.10%; Melting Point (°C): 128-130 °C; Elemental Analysis: C, 54.82; H, 3.38; N, 15.78; FTIR (KBr) (Spectra No.-86): -NH₂ (2-Peaks): 3246 cm⁻¹ and 3286 cm⁻¹, aromatic ring (3-Peaks): 1512 cm⁻¹, 1590 cm⁻¹ and 1671 cm⁻¹, Ar-OCH₃: 1296 cm⁻¹, Ar-OH: 3500 cm⁻¹, Ar-2,4,5Cl: 1078 cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (500.13 MHz, DMSO-d₆, δ ppm): 6.97-8.07 (m, 5H, Ar-H),

9.69 (s, 2H, -NH₂), 9.77 (s, 1H, -OH), 3.70 (s, 3H, OCH₃), 3.40 (s, 2H, CH₂)

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Chemistry:

The starting compounds of bis-chalcones **3a-j** were prepared by the reaction of substituted N-phenyl-piperidine-2,6-dione **1a-j** using 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy Benzaldehyde **2**. The series of amino-pyrimidines or 9-(1-phenyl)-4,5-(2'',''-methoxyphenol)-9H-1,3,6,8,9-hexa-azo-fluorene-2,7-diamine (**6a-j**) were synthesized in reasonable yields by the microwave irradiation of bis-chalcones **3a-j** with guanidine nitrate **4** in presence of neutral alumina by solvent free state. The structure of amino-pyrimidines was confirmed by elemental, IR and ¹H NMR analysis.

Table 1
Antimicrobial activities of Bis-chalcones and amino-pyrimidines

Compd Code	Zone diameter calculated in mm and tabulated by (Mean±S.D.)			
	<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Candida albicans</i>	<i>Aspergillusniger</i>
	100 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	100 µg/ml	100 µg/ml
3a	--	--	16.31 ± 0.33 **	16.46 ± 0.27 **
3b	--	2.33±4.04 **	17.80 ± 0.16 **	17.36 ± 0.31 **
3c	8.33±0.57 **	8.33±0.57 **	22.42 ± 0.39 **	21.69 ± 0.18 **
3d	7.33±0.57 **	4.66±4.04 **	21.41 ± 0.25 **	19.50 ± 0.45 **
3e	--	--	14.53 ± 0.41 **	16.56 ± 1.75 **
3f	8.33±0.57 **	8.33±0.57 **	16.15 ± 0.22 **	18.57 ± 0.32 **
3g	--	2.33±4.04 **	20.43 ± 0.16 **	17.12 ± 0.12 **
3h	--	--	19.04 ± 0.08 **	15.89 ± 1.72 **
3i	--	--	17.71 ± 0.22 **	16.31 ± 0.22 **
3j	7.66±1.15 **	2.33±4.04 **	19.94 ± 0.15 **	21.67 ± 0.48 **
5a	6.33±0.57 **	7.66±0.57 **	--	10.23 ± 0.38 **
5b	6.66±1.15 **	8±1 **	22.57 ± 0.27 **	16.72 ± 0.20 **
5c	7.33±1.52 **	8.66±0.57 **	13.83 ± 0.22 **	12.56 ± 0.08 **
5d	7.33±1.52 **	7.66±1.15 **	--	19.13 ± 0.06 **
5e	6.66±0.57 **	7.33±0.57 **	8.69 ± 0.39 **	15.36 ± 0.30 **
5f	7.66±0.57 **	8.33±0.57 **	9.34 ± 0.34 **	15.71 ± 0.29 **
5g	7.33±0.57 **	8.66±0.57 **	16.57 ± 0.40 **	19.54 ± 0.39 **
5h	7.33±0.57 **	4.66±4.04 **	8.86 ± 0.22 **	12.56 ± 0.13 **
5i	6.33±0.57 **	7±0 **	11.30 ± 0.32 **	18.59 ± 0.20 **
5j	6.33±0.57 **	7.33±0.57 **	8.40 ± 0.04 **	20.73 ± 0.44 **
Ctrl	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0	0.0±0.0
Std	18.33±0.57	18.33±0.57	12.40 ± 0.43	10.45 ± 0.11

Keynote: Zone of inhibition measured in mm (Mean±S.D.) (N=3) ('--' means no zone)

Antimicrobial activities (3a-j and 5a-j):

The entire synthesized compounds **3a-j** and **5a-j** were screened for their antibacterial activity against gram positive bacteria *Bacillus subtilis* (MCMB-310) and gram negative bacteria *Escherichia coli* (MCMB-301) using DMF solvent. And antifungal activities against *Candida albicans* (NCIM-3471) and *Aspergillus niger* (NCIM-545) strains using DMSO solvent. Ampicillin for antibacterial activities and Amphotericin-B for antifungal activities were used as a standard. All the results of synthesized compounds were carried out by the triplicate format N=3 with Mean $\pm$ SD. The statistical significance was carried out by one way ANOVA and confirmed by Dunnett multiple comparisons test performed the standard drugs against synthesized compounds. P value < 0.05 was considered as statistically significant remarked by * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$ compared to standard groups. The calculated data were enlisted in the table-1;

CONCLUSION

An entire new series of amino-pyrimidine containing 4-hydroxy-3-methoxy benzylidene root have been synthesized in one pot and facile manner from bis-heterocyclic chalcones in good yield. A good number of the synthesized bis-chalcone **3a-j** and amino-pyrimidines **5a-j** showed superior and synergistic antifungal activities against *Candida albicans* and *Aspergillus niger* fungal strains.

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